

Evaluation of Nutrient Status of Soils Under *Parkia biglobosa* for Sustainable Production and Climate Change Mitigation in Ogbomosho, South West, Nigeria

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Abstracts

The African locust bean (*Parkia biglobosa*) is a multi-purpose tree that is commonly retained on small-holder farms in the savanna region of West Africa. Nutrient status of soils under African locust bean was evaluated to ascertain the effects of the tree on soil physical and chemical properties and suggest management practices needed for an increased production and climate change mitigation. This study was carried out in Ogbomosho North, Orire and Surulere Local Government Areas of Oyo state, Nigeria. Nine villages in Ogbomosho North (Lautech farm, katangua, Amama), Orire (Fedegbo, Obamo, Olooru) and Surulere (Oloose, Iregba and Iresa) Local Government areas were randomly selected based on the predominance of farming occupation over other occupations in the local government areas. Soil samples were collected in triplicate with the aid of a soil auger. In each village, three farms planted each with *Parkia biglobosa* were sampled at the depth of 0-20cm with the use of soil auger for physical and chemical analysis in the laboratory. Organic carbon was variably low and medium between villages of the study area of parkia canopy. Micro nutrients such as Iron, copper, zinc and manganese were very high, exchangeable magnesium and potassium were high. Calcium is medium while nitrogen, phosphorus and sodium are low in soil under the tree canopy. The build-up of organic carbon under the tree was not substantial due to frequent cultivation that involved site burning that destroys plant litter that would have been converted into soil organic matter when allowed to decompose in situ. Furthermore, growth of parkia trees and seedlings will be retarded in areas with predominantly sandy soils and this should be taken into consideration in afforestation, community forestry and shelterbelt projects involving the establishment of parkia trees.

Keywords: Sustainable Production, Climate change mitigation; Farming community; Assessment

Introduction

The African locust bean tree, *Parkia biglobosa* is a perennial tree legume which has been known to be a native of Africa and is an important multipurpose tree of West African Savannah land (Olorunmaiye *et al.*, 2011), which is primarily grown for its pods that contain both a sweet pulp and valuable seeds (Abdulhamid *et al.*, 2017). African locust bean tree are used for medicinal purposes, source of shelter and litter for the soil (Houndonougbo, 2020), it is an essential function ecologically in cycling of nutrients from deep soils, and in holding the soil particles with the aid of the roots to prevent soil erosion (Alabi *et al.*, 2005). The seed is useful ingredients for consumption and high in protein, carbohydrate and is a good source of fat and calcium for rural dwellers (Ntui *et al.*, 2012). *Parkia biglobosa* is beneficial to the soil situated beneath, which is made useful and valuable by the dung and urine of animals that shelter under the tree's shade. It can also be used as timber for making pestles,

mortars, bows, and seats (Ntui *et al.*, 2012). The pods and husks have also been discovered to be good food for livestock. The various importance of *Parkia biglobosa* made it an ideal plant to promote across Africa, as it combines in a single species two of Africa's greatest needs which are; food security and tree cover alongside the health benefits.

The carbon sequestration potential of tropical land use systems had been a subject of interest to the dual goal of climate change mitigation and soil productivity improvement. Land use conversion and agricultural activities have been reported to produce 30% of total anthropogenic emissions both directly and indirectly. Adaptation to global climate change through improved soil quality by the adoption of improved management practices is key to maintaining sustainable agricultural production (Owoade and Abolarin., 2021). Change in soil properties can vary markedly with the type of land cover change, climate and method, the extent of

vegetation removal (e.g. land clearing, fires, and mechanical harvest) and management.

Soils as an important reservoir for numerous substances, organism and habitat for animals and plants have been exposed to various degradation activities from human disturbance and climate change such as global warming, ozone depletion, pollution have great impact on soils (Pouyat et al., 2002). Extensive degrading agricultural lands is a major problem deterring Nigerian from achieving food security. Also, poor soil management strategies and intense cultivation also leads to consistent soil degradation all over the country (Oyetola et al., 2021). Since soil can lose their quantity and quality within a short period, there should be sustainable use of soil resources and basic knowledge and assessment of changes in soil properties and their states is required to evaluate the impacts of different management practices. Soil properties affect many processes in soil which make it suitable for agricultural practices and other purposes. Assessing soil quality involves measuring soil properties and using the measured values to detect changes in soil as a result of land use or management practices.

In West Africa, numerous studies were carried out on the nutritional composition of the seeds (Alabi et al., 2005; Esenwah and Ikenebomeh, 2008; Elemo et al., 2011), medical uses of the plant (Kouadio et al., 2000; Odetola et al., 2006; El-Mahmood and Ameh, 2007). It is important to note that Aweto (2013) pointed out that vegetation and the soil are functionally interdependent and they exert reciprocal effect on one another. Similarly, the studies on the biomass parameters of locust bean trees in small holder farms in West Africa (Odebisi et al., 2004; Delvaux et al., 2010; Sanou et al., 2012, 2017; Padakale et al., 2015; Chabi et al., 2016, Oyerinde et al., 2018) did not examine the properties of the soil underneath the trees. It is also pertinent to observe that studies that quantified the biomass of other tree species in West Africa (Guendehou et al., 2012; Mbow et al., 2014; Goussanou et al., 2016) also did not examine the characteristics of the soil underneath the tree species. This study was therefore evaluated to ascertain the effects of the tree on soil physical and chemical properties and suggest management practices needed for an increased production and climate change mitigation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1. Experimental site

This study was carried out in Ogbomoso North, Orire and Surulere Local Government Areas of Oyo state, Nigeria. Nine villages in Lautech farm, katangua, Amama (Ogbomoso North), Fedegbo, Obama, Olooru (Orire Local Government), Oloose, Iregba and Iresa (Surulere Local Government) were randomly selected. The choice of these locations

were based on the predominance of farming occupation over other occupations in the local government areas. The climate of Ogbomoso area can be described as fairly hot, tropical, with marked wet and dry seasons, usually with a short period of harmattan in between. Mean annual rainfall is about 1400 mm while the mean annual temperature is about 27°C. The vegetation can be referred to as Southern Guinea Savannah. (Owoade, 2020).

Ogbomoso is located between Latitude 8°2'35.20"N and 8°14'34.25"N and Longitude 4°10'52.92"E and 4°19'40.59"E. 104 km North East of Ibadan, 58 km North West of Osogbo, 57 km South West of Ilorin and 53 km North East of Oyo. Cultivated lands of the study areas are primarily used for farming activities.

3.2 Soil Sampling and Laboratory Analysis

Soil samples were collected in triplicate with the aid of a soil auger. In each village, three farms planted each with *Parkia biglobosa* were sampled. Soils were collected from the farmland randomly at the depth of 0-20cm for physical and chemical analysis in the laboratory. The samples were bulked to form a composite and air dried, crushed and sieved through 2 and 0.5 mm meshes for the determination of pH, particle size, C, N, P, exchangeable cations (K, Mg, Ca, Na) and extractable micronutrients (Mn, Fe, Cu, Zn). The bulk density of each land use was taken 0-5cm and 10-15cm with core samplers.

Laboratory analyses were carried out at the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA), Ibadan. Particle size analysis was carried out with the aid of hydrometer using sodium hexametaphosphate as the dispersant (AOAC, 1990). Soil pH was determined in 1:1 soil water ratio (Black, 1965). Total nitrogen (N) was extracted by the macro – Kjeldahl digestion method (Bremner and Mulvaney, 1982) followed by colorimetric determination using Technicon Auto- analyser. Mehlich 3 (a multipurpose extractant) was used to extract available phosphorus, exchangeable cations (K, Mg, Ca and Na) and extractable micronutrients (Mn, Fe, Cu and Zn) (Mehlich, 1984). Phosphorus was determined colorimetrically using Technicon Auto- analyser, while the concentration of (calcium, magnesium, Copper, Zinc, Iron and Manganese) in the extract was determined by Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer. Sodium (Na) and Potassium (K) was determined using Flame emission photometer. Exchangeable acidity was determined by KCl extraction. CEC was determined by summation of Exchangeable bases (K, Mg, Ca and Na) and Exchangeable acidity. Organic carbon was determined by chronic acid digestion method (Heanes, 1984).

3.3 Determination of Bulk Density

The soil bulk density was evaluated using core method (Cresswell and Hamilton, 2002) as follows:

$$BD \text{ (g/cm}^3\text{)} = \frac{\text{weight of oven dry soil (g)}}{\text{Volume of core (cm}^3\text{)}}$$

Where BD = bulk density (g/cm³), volume of core = $\pi r^2 h$

Where $\pi = 3.142$, h = height of the cylinder, r = internal radius of the cylinder

3.4 Determination of Carbon stock

The soil carbon stocks (C_{st}) were computed for the top 20 cm using the equation:

$$C_{st} = A \times \rho_b \times Z \times SOC$$

(1)

where A is the land area (1 ha = 104 m²), ρ_b is the soil bulk density (kg/m³) and z is the soil depth (0.20 m) (Owoade et al., 2020).

Results and Discussion

The mean physiographic characteristics of parkia in the study area.

The mean physiographic characteristics of parkia in the study area are presented in Table 1. The diameter breadth height (DBH) of the sampled trees ranged between 96-266cm. The height of most of the trees sampled ranged between 10.5-18.83m. The elevation of the area where data was collected ranged between 320-433.33m. The physiographic characteristics is suggesting that the locust bean trees sampled are mature and are likely to have been growing on the farmland for several decades to enable them exert significant effects on the soil underneath their canopies.

The physical properties of soil under locust bean in Ogbomoso agricultural zone.

Irrespective of local government, the soil under parkia trees was sandy loam (Table 2). The bulk density were high for all the local government sampled. It ranges between 1.52-2.06g/cm³. Soil texture is an important physical property of soils that is not easily changed by humans as a result of changes in land use (Brady & Weil 2014). The soil under parkia in all the local government areas is texturally similar. Hence, any observed differences between them in respect of soil physical and chemical properties, cannot be attributed to effects of tree (Aweto & Dikinya 2003). The bulk density for LAUTECH soil is high while the other villages in the study areas are very high. High bulk density is an indicator of low soil porosity and soil compaction. High bulk density impacts available water capacity, root growth and movement of air and water through soil. Compaction increases bulk density and reduces crop yields and vegetative cover available to protect soil from erosion.

The chemical properties of soil under locust bean in Ogbomoso agricultural zone.

Table 3 shows the chemical properties of soils in ogbomoso agricultural zone. The three local government area had significant effects on the soil pH while the villages did not significantly influence the pH content. The highest soil pH (6.84) which indicates a slightly acidic status was obtained from Obama village in Orire local government which was significantly higher than the soil pH at Amama, Iregba and Olooru which recorded the lowest soil pH (6.36). The soil pH can influence the solubility and availability of nutrients in the soil. This indicated that the soil was moderately acidic. The moderate acidity of the soil might be as a result of the leaching of basic cations or due to incessant uptake by crop. The moderate acidity implied that nutrients are likely to be available for crop uptake. Odunze et al. (2006) asserted that the pH range of 5.5- 6.5 is optimum for the release of plant nutrients. The soil pH can vary within short distance due to nitrification, root activity, and decomposition of organic matter. According to Chemedo et al, the pH of grassland soils was higher than that of the soils in cultivated land and forest land. But, Yimer et al. have found that the pH of cultivated land soils was higher than that of the soils in grassland and forest land. The reason for lower soil pH in the Eucalyptus woodlot can be due to frequent cation uptake and removal of cations around the tree [11]. Nitrogen, Phosphorus, Sodium and organic carbon present in the soil are low in all the local government area. Calcium and Organic carbon in the soil are moderate in all the local government except in Obama, Iregba and Iresa. Phosphorus and Magnesium in the soil are high for all the local governments studied. . This result is primarily due to the predominantly sandy nature of the soils, the farming practice of burning the cut slash of fallow vegetation prior to cultivation and savannah vegetation burning during the cut slash of fallow period.

The mean soil organic matter of the soil samples was found to be 2.61% (Table 1). According to guidelines for rating soil fertility indicators suggested by ILACO, 1985 and Landon, 1991, the soil had high amount of organic matter content. The high level of soil organic matter in the study area could be attributed to the high return of litter or agricultural residues to the soils.

The villages have no significant effect on the phosphorus. In general, the soils are deficient in available phosphorus and phosphorus deficiency is likely to be an important factor limiting crop yield as the levels of the nutrient are well below 10mgkg. The low phosphorus status of soils can be adduced to the practice of burning prior to cultivation, frequent cultivation and the slow rate of organic matter accretion in savanna fallow soil.

In contrast to the level of phosphorus, the level of potassium in the soil under parkia is high. There were however, a significant build-up of exchangeable calcium and a decrease in the mean

level of effective cation exchangeable capacity (ECEC) in the soil under parkia.

The micronutrients properties of soils under locust bean

Table 4 shows the micronutrients properties of soils of locust bean in ogbomoso Agricultural zone. Irrespective of all the local government the micronutrients are very high (zinc, copper, iron and Manganese)

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Despite the fact that the land is cultivated at frequent intervals in the study area, the African locust bean trees retained on the farmland have some beneficial effects on the soil underneath their

canopies. The build- up of organic carbon under the tree was not substantial due to frequent cultivation that involved site burning that destroys plant liter that would have been converted into soil organic matter when allowed to decompose in situ.

The pH of the soil is slightly acidic, which resulted into low level of some chemical soil property such as Nitrogen, Phosphorus, Sodium, organic carbon virtually in all the study area, while all the micronutrients are higher for the local government with high bulk density of the soil.

The soil is generally low for most of the nutrient parameters. Therefore, organic manure should be applied for improved crop productivity and yield

Table 1: The mean physiographic characteristics of Parkia in the study area.

	VILLAGES	DBH (CM)	HEIGHT (M)	DISTANCE (M)	ELEVATION (M)	GPS
Ogbomoso North	LAUTECH	265.67	14.63	10	343.33	8°10'1''N4°16'14''E
	Amama	234.33	17.5	10	350	8°9'31''N4°16'8''E
	Katangua	121	12.07	10	320	8°8'42''N4°15'43''E
Orire	Obamo	146	12.16	10	433.33	8°18'58''N4°5'58''E
	Fedegbo	302	12.49	10	400	8°16'40''N4°8'8''E
	Olooru	234.33	18.83	10	370	8°20'43''N4°10'17''E
Surulere	Oloose	155.33	15.53	10	346.67	8°6'34''N4°22'39''E
	Iregba	96	10.5	10	373.33	8°6'37''N4°22'42''E
	Iresa	208.33	16.8	10	370	8°6'37''N4°22'43''E

N.B

DBH: Diameter Breadth Height

GPS: Global Positioning System .

LGA : Local Government Area

Table 2: Physical properties of soil under locust beans in Ogbomoso Agricultural zone.

LGA	VILLAGES	Clay (%)	Sand (%)	Silt (%)	Soil Texture	Bulk Density (g/cm ³)
Ogbomoso North	Lautech	11.96	80.22	7.81	Sandy loam	1.52
	Katangua	12.30	79.22	8.48	Sandy loam	2.31
	Amama	10.30	82.22	7.48	Sandy loam	2.02
Orire	Obamo	10.30	83.33	6.37	Sandy loam	1.90
	Fedegbo	11.96	79.33	8.70	Sandy loam	1.89
	Olooru	12.30	79.00	8.70	Sandy loam	2.06
Surulere	Iresa	13.07	77.78	9.15	Sandy loam	1.91
	Oloose	10.74	82.22	6.81	Sandy loam	1.95
	Iregba	10.74	81.44	7.81	Sandy loam	1.99
LSD LGA		0.83**	1.81**	1.21ns		0.14**
LSD VILLAGES		1.45**	3.12*	2.10ns		0.25**

N.B:

LGA: Local Government Area.

Table 3: Chemical properties of soil under locust bean in Ogbomoso Agricultural zone.

LGA	VILLAGE	pH	OC (g/kg)	N (%)	P (mg/kg)	Ca	Mg (cmol/kg)	K	Na	ECEC	TSC(ha)
Ogbomoso North	Lautech	6.71	1.15	0.074	4.78	4.47	1.09	0.365	0.071	6.00	35517
	Katangua	6.54	1.16	0.071	0.32	3.49	1.28	0.508	0.057	5.34	54391
	Amama	6.49	1.02	0.070	5.06	3.88	1.01	0.392	0.064	5.35	41943
Orire	Fedegbo	6.54	1.21	0.077	3.92	4.06	1.09	0.412	0.067	5.64	46559
	Obamo	6.84	0.90	0.063	3.02	3.82	1.04	0.407	0.058	5.33	33677
	Olooru	6.36	1.23	0.076	2.58	3.96	1.24	0.446	0.067	5.17	51614
Surulere	Iresa	6.69	0.98	0.066	3.05	3.55	1.17	0.491	0.043	5.25	38444
	Oloose	6.56	1.38	0.092	3.44	4.75	1.36	0.463	0.084	6.66	54232
	Iregba	6.49	0.97	0.058	3.02	3.45	0.85	0.311	0.064	4.77	38444
LSD LGA		0.17**	0.25*	0.019*	1.83**	0.90**	0.34**	0.142ns	0.013ns	1,32**	11596.3**
LSD Villages		0.29ns	0.45ns	0.034ns	3.18ns	1.58ns	0.59ns	0.246ns	0.023ns	2.29ns	20085.3ns

ECEC: Effective cation exchange capacity.

TSC: Total soil carbon. LGA: Local government area

Table 4: Micronutrients properties of soils under locust bean

LGA	VILLAGE	Cu(mg/kg)	Fe(mg/kg)	Mn(mg/kg)	Zn(mg/kg)
Ogbon	Lautech	8.52	91.0	98.4	43.6
	Katangua	8.23	113.0	161.7	12.6
	Amama	7.66	81.7	111.5	47.5
Orire	Fedegbo	7.66	89.6	138.8	40.6
	Obamo	9.95	97.1	133.1	31.2
	Olooru	6.79	99.0	99.6	31.8
Surulere	Iresa	7.27	81.1	135.8	30.4
	Oloose	8.42	95.3	127.4	30.9
	Iregba	8.71	109.3	108.3	33.4
LSD LGA		1.89*	12.06**	23.97**	19.64**
LSD Villages		3.28ns	20.89*	41.57ns	34.02ns

LGA: Local government area.

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